

pers and leafolders. Tests conducted by the AICRIP plant physiology section show Govind can sustain drought for 9 days during the vegetative stage. It is a low tillering variety and should use closer spacing (20 cm × 10 cm) with 2-3 seedlings/hill when transplanted. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Ratoon rice can yield well

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Nine medium-duration rice cultivars were tested for ratoon growth and yield in a randomized block design with three replications during 1980-81 dry season in West Bengal, India. Four of the cultivars were also grown as a main crop during 1980 wet season.

The dry season crop was harvested in summer and allowed to grow as a ratoon crop during 1981-82 wet season. Nitrogen at 20 kg/ha was topdressed during early vegetative phase and pesticide was sprayed prior to flowering. No irrigation was used because 1,000 mm rainfall fell during crop growth.

Some cultivars showed good ratooning ability and matured about 14 days earlier

Grain yield and days to maturity of rice grown as a main crop in wet and dry seasons and as a ratoon crop after the dry season crop. West Bengal, India, 1980-82.

Cultivar	Main crop				Ratoon crop	
	Grain yield (t/ha)		Days to maturity		Grain yield (t/ha)	Days to maturity
	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season		
IET3273	3.4	3.9	115	130	1.8	101
IET3305		4.2		130	1.2	101
IET3306		3.4		130	0.5	101
IET3629	2.4	4.8	110	140	2.7	95
IET3630	3.1	3.9	114	130	1.5	101
IET4555		4.7		140	2.1	95
IET5857	3.3	3.1	118	130	0.4	101
Ratna		4.5		130	0.6	101
Local		3.8		130	0.7	101
CD (0.05)		0.46			0.27	

than the main wet season crop and a month earlier than the main dry season crop.

IET3629 yielded highest (2.7 t/ha) in the shortest time (95 days) (see table). Its ratoon yield was 12% higher than main crop yield in wet season and 44%

less than main crop yield in dry season. It matured 15 days (wet season) and 45 days (dry season) earlier than the main crops.

Other cultivars with good ratooning ability were IET4555 (2.1 t/ha) and IET3273 (1.8 t/ha). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Sheath rot incidence in cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels

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Incidence of sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* was recorded for 26 rice cultivars that received 50, 100, 150, and 200 kg N/ha at CRR farm during 1981 kharif. Only Pankaj showed resistance at all nitrogen levels. Six cultivars were moderately resistant, 8 were moderately susceptible, and 11 were susceptible (see table).

In general, sheath rot susceptibility

Reaction to sheath rot of 26 rice cultivars grown at different nitrogen levels, CRR, Cuttack, India, kharif 1981.

Cultivars	Disease score ^d at different nitrogen levels			
	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	200 kg/ha
Pankaj	0	0	0	0
	<i>Resistant</i>			
	<i>Moderately resistant</i>			
CR294-548-1, RTM68	0	1	3	3
Jagannath, IR28, IR36	1	3	3	3
IR8	0	3	3	3
	<i>Moderately susceptible</i>			
CR318-461	1	3	3	5
CR318-549, PR106	1	3	5	5
CR316-639-1, IR4432-664-2	1	5	5	5
IR2071-178-3, CR.316-639-2, IR4432-664-1	3	3	5	5
	<i>Susceptible</i>			
CR318-548-7	1	3	3	7

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increased with increased nitrogen from 50 to 200 kg/ha.

October 1981, when most of the cultivars were in the boot or flowering stage, was unusually dry (total rainfall 22.7 mm), with a minimum temperature of 23.1°C, maximum temperature 41°C, 77% relative humidity, and 8.9 hours sunshine. The dry weather appears to have favored sheath rot. □

TABLE CONTINUED

Cultivars	Disease score ^a at different nitrogen levels			
	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	200 kg/ha
CR294-28-1, CR294-548-2	1	3	7	7
CR294-548-3, CR315-621	1	5	7	7
ET4141	3	5	5	7
Jaya, Ramkrishna	5	5	7	7
PR107	5	7	7	7
BG90-2	0	7	7	7
CR188-10	1	3	5	7

^a 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible.

Screening of rice varieties for resistance to ragged stunt disease

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Seeds of 47 rice varieties collected from southern and central China (Guangdong, Guang Xi, Hu Nan, Hu Bei, Jiang Xi, and Fu Jian Provinces) were sown in seedboxes. At the 3- to 4-leaf stage, 34 viruliferous brown planthopper adults were released on each plant and allowed to feed for 3 days. Seedlings were transplanted to the paddy field.

All test varieties were susceptible, except IR36 with an infection rate of 12.5% (see table). Highly susceptible Guang Lu Ai 4, Bai Zhen Long, Zhen Long 13, and Hong 410 were severely stunted. Tall varieties had no significant stunting at the early stage, but were severely stunted at later stages.

Some varieties first showed leaf twisting and later ragged leaf symptoms.

Varietal resistance to ragged stunt, Guangdong, China, 1980.

Variety	Inoculated (no.)	In-fected (no.)	In-fec-tion (%)	Variety	Inoculated (no.)	In-fected (no.)	In-fec-tion (%)
IR36	32	4	12.5	Gui Chao Ai	39	38	97.4
IR29	20	6	30.0	Bai Yi Wan 1	30	30	100
Yu Chi 231-8	30	15	50.0	Guang Lu Ai4	25	25	100
Guang Yu 73	28	21	75.0	Hong 408	35	35	100
76-116	29	22	75.9	Guang Er 104	18	18	100
PII 299	30	24	80.0	Bai Zhen Long	34	34	100
PII 292	27	23	85.2	IR206 1	12	12	100
78-804	18	16	88.9	IR26	34	34	100
75-89	29	26	89.7	Qiang Hong 35-2	22	22	100
Shan You 2	23	21	91.3	Quan Ye Bai	30	30	100
75013	24	22	91.7	22-3	29	29	100
PII 293	21	25	92.6	150	25	25	100
91228	29	27	93.1	Hong 410	25	25	100
7055	29	27	93.1	Zhan Long 13	29	29	100
Wu Dong 51	15	14	93.3	Yuan Feng Zao	28	28	100
Nong Ken 58	25	24	96.0	Zhu Bian Xuan	26	26	100
Si You 2	27	26	96.3	Cong Siu Qing	23	23	100
E-Wan 3	27	26	96.3	5450	30	30	100
73-151	28	27	96.4	5180	20	20	100
PII 298	29	28	96.6	Gan Nan Wan	30	30	100
Er Jiu Qing	30	29	96.7	15-5	30	30	100
Shan You 3	30	29	96.7	PII 291	29	29	100
PII 300	30	29	96.7	TN1	28	28	100
Xiang Ai Zao	31	30	96.8				

Others first showed ragged leaf symptoms and later leaf twisting. Still others first had vein-swelling symptoms. In

severely affected plants panicles did not exert. The plants became shorter and shorter and finally died. □

A note on rice blast in Tanzania

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Rice blast incited by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most prevalent rice disease in Tanzania, but no empirical data on the extent of losses from it are available.

An experiment was conducted at Morogoro, central-eastern Tanzania, to determine the extent of loss caused by blast. Two rice cultivars — Kihogo Red (resistant to blast) and Faya Theresa (susceptible) — were planted in a split-

plot experiment with five replications under irrigation in February 1980. The cultivars were randomly allocated to the main plots. There was no artificial inoculation; the disease developed from natural inoculum. Fungicide treatment (spraying vs no spraying) was randomly allocated to the subplots to generate different disease levels. The fungicide benomyl (Benlate 50 WP) at 1 kg ai/ha was sprayed 6 times at 2-week intervals starting 46 days after planting. Control plots were sprayed with water. Disease severity was assessed four times and scored using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Disease differences were highly significant between the resistant and susceptible cultivars, and between the sprayed and unsprayed plots of the susceptible Faya Theresa (see figure).

The rice was harvested in July 1980 then sun-dried, threshed, winnowed, and weighed (adjusted to 14% moisture content). Paddy yields per hectare and 1,000-paddy grain weight in the sprayed and unsprayed plants of the two cultivars are in the table. There was an 18% reduction in yield and an 11% reduction in 1,000-grain weight in Faya Theresa. Both reductions were highly significant. Disease by